

CERTIFICATE

◆◆◆ THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO ◆◆◆

O'ZBEKISTONDA TA'LIM-TARBIYA JARAYONIGA INNOVATSION
YONDASHUVLAR.MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR MAVZUSIDA RESPUBLIKA
ILMIY ONLINE KONFERENSIYASIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Rakhmatullayeva Dilobar Erkinovna

EFFECTIVENESS OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE CLASSROOM

**NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN
TAQDIRLANADI**

2023/SENTABR

